

IMPROVING AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS EXPORT SYSTEM

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Annotation. The article highlights the ways to expand the opportunities for export of agricultural products and offers suggestions for its promotion.

Keywords. Agricultural Products, Exports, Imports, World Market, Consumer, Incentives, Tax Incentives, Subsidies, Customs Benefits, Export Premiums, Export Credits

Login. The development of scientific proposals and practical recommendations aimed at ensuring the stability of foreign trade in our country, further increasing the export potential, and eliminating negative external influences on export-import operations allows determining the relevance of this scientific article and the scope of the issues to be solved in it.

To develop export, first of all, it is necessary to produce a product that is a buyer in the world market, and with its quality and appearance, it will be acceptable to foreign consumers. When it comes to agricultural products, in order for these products to be bought in the world market, not only the taste, but also the packaging, quality and appearance should be excellent.

Such positive changes in the structure of foreign trade turnover are the results of the economic policy aimed at the attention directed to this sector, in particular the comprehensive promotion of export-oriented production and support for the production of import-substituting products.

Promotion of export of agricultural products.

Promotion of export-oriented production includes:

- tax benefits;
- subsidies;
- guaranteeing private investments;
- preferential loans;
- helping to solve infrastructure issues;
- promotion of attracting foreign direct investments, etc.

Direct export promotion consists of the following:

- Export awards;
- Export credits;
- Seasonal loans for export; - Export insurance;
- Tax benefits;
- Customs privileges;
- Encouragement of foreign direct investments, etc.

Agricultural products are an important component of the general system of export financing system and tax regulation, export promotion. Among them, export guarantees and pre-export crediting are the most effective. In it, medium and long-term lending should take the main place.

In conditions of limited budget funds, state support can be implemented not only by preferential state loans, but also by attracting private commercial loans under state guarantee. This helps to improve lending conditions and reduce credit risks.

One of the components of the support system for the export of agricultural products is the insurance of export credits against commercial and political risks to ensure the protection of national exporters, as well as the insurance of export operations for the development of foreign markets.

In order to implement these measures, it is necessary to activate the work of banks in the republic.

Reforming the tax system is also considered as one of the important directions for promoting the export of agricultural products.

Within the framework of improving the tax system of Uzbekistan and strengthening its stimulating effect on national producers of goods, it is appropriate to use the following forms of tax incentives for exporters:

Legal, economic, organizational and international support of national exporters should be the basis of the foreign trade promotion system. Its influence should start from production and end with the sale of products on the world market and their service.

It can be considered as the country's competitiveness of the product-producing

industry. There are internal and external connections between these steps. The competitiveness of the country and industry is determined by the ability of a particular producer to produce competitive goods. The consumption, price and quality characteristics of this product are determined by comparison with similar products and determine its success in the domestic and foreign markets. At present, factors such as product price, novelty, science capacity and scientific potential, and environmental cleanliness are of great importance in international competitiveness. Many countries in the world ensure the competitiveness of their products through the use of innovations and the production of products with high technological characteristics. This requires extensive development of scientific and technological potential. In developed countries, the value of scientific and technical and experimental construction works is growing at a high rate and constitutes half of the value of a new product.

During the research, it is desirable to determine the level of competitiveness of farm products using the method of determining the relative efficiency or relative advantages between agricultural products, which is widely used in the experience of foreign countries, that is, the value of internal resources.

Summary. One of the components of the support system for the export of agricultural products is the insurance of export credits against commercial and political risks to ensure the protection of national exporters, as well as the insurance of export operations for the development of foreign markets. In order to implement these measures, it is necessary to activate the work of banks in the republic.

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